

INTERACTIVE ACTIVITIES AND EFFECTIVE METHODS OF DISTANCE LEARNING IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *This article is dedicated to develop effective distance learning methods for teaching English classes through a comprehensive approach that takes into consideration the unique learning needs of students and evolving nature of teaching practices. There are some effective ways to develop a successful distance learning program for English language classes.*

Key words: *Distance, learning, technology, requirements, technical, specialist, space, resources, effective, approach, language, foreign.*

The modern world has entered a period of global changes and intercultural communications in various spheres of human activity and needs highly qualified specialists with deep knowledge of foreign languages.

Distance education is becoming a new standard for higher education in Uzbekistan.

Distance education, especially for specialists, already who own one profession and want to improve their skills in the field of English as a language of international communication for the purpose of exercising their professional activities at a higher quality level and for the purpose of professional communication with foreign partners. They manifest the desire to learn foreign languages remotely, with good quality and get a second diploma, because in teaching a foreign language they see an opportunity to advance their careers.

Distance learning of foreign languages is advancing in the world, universities offer programs and courses for learning foreign languages online. British, Canadian, American universities offer many distance learning programs in foreign languages: The University of Dundee, The Open University (GB) and so on.

Over the past two or three years, the faculty of continuous higher education in the Jizzakh State Pedagogical University and world languages them. Uzbekistan World language University, The National University, along with the traditional academic program, also implement a distance learning program in foreign languages for students from different regions of Uzbekistan who wish to receive second higher education in translation case.

With traditional and mixed forms of education, students have sufficient opportunities for active learning of a foreign language, to optimize their speech (written and oral) skills and competencies in the presence of training partners in the group, a teacher in the classroom. Unlike traditional learning, the distance form does not imply direct contact with teachers and speech participants in the dialogue, polylogue. She aims at independent activity of the student in an individual mode. There is a problem in active language acquisition. This problem can remove if you build the educational process on an electronic platform, setting the content of e-learning, pedagogically aimed at activation of individual activity with using active learning methods. lack of real learning conditions for direct communication in a foreign language, pair or group work, direct collaboration with teacher is a problem of distance education, especially foreign language, which naturally implies the communication of a nikant-partner, the distance of the student from teacher and from their communicative group partners. Educational work of students should not be carried out in passive learning. There is a need to find ways activation of the educational communicative activity of the student in the conditions of individualized, remote learning in the mode of distance learning technologies (DET).

The main research method was determined by the qualitative (descriptive) and quantitative approach, observation and interpretation.

Qualitative research made it possible to analyze and interpret active techniques, set out in the development of the lessons. The technology platform is distance learning system Moodle with USWLU as the main means of delivery and organization of educational activities of student comrades. The Moodle online system was used to individual training, and Skype video for contact consultations of the teacher with students.

All students completed their studies within academic year and positively passed intermediate exams at the end of semesters in a foreign language, performing language and speech tests in the FCE/CAE format. The results were recorded in writing tests and in oral form according to the specified parameters and criteria. The process of learning activity of an individual student in remote mode was captured in videos. Distance education (DL) as an element of open education is learning on distance. DL is used by students who, for various reasons, cannot attend contact lessons. They work from home or from the office and study the e-course on their own, complete tasks and interact with each other and with the teacher through Internet. In other words, they take on responsibility for their autonomous learning. N. Sampson (Sampson 2003: 104) defines distance learning as independent distance learning with the help of texts for self-study and remote communication. As Holmberg (1989: 24) points out, people prefer distance

learning convenience, flexibility and adaptability of this mode education to meet the individual needs of students. Most Accurate definition of distance education we we find in M. Simonson: “Distance education is now often defined as: institution-based, formal education where the learning group is separated, and where interactive telecommunications systems are used to connect learners, resources, and instructors.” Pedagogical aspects of distance learning of foreign languages are gradually analyzed and studied in the literature. Teaching foreign languages through remote technologies is reflected in a number of publications. So, in a monograph O. Tarnopolsky, an innovative constructivist approach is analyzed with a mixed teaching English for special goals and professional communication on university level. Here are described issues of active language learning both in the classroom and outside the classroom independent work, including

Internet - active methods (role-playing game, simulation of professional activity, project work, case studies, discussions, etc.¹ The author uses the term experiential learning for experiential learning that forms the conditions for active learning. Involving students in the acquisition process knowledge and skills development. An analysis of the literature shows that distance education in universities, its principles and organization, technical equipment are widely represented in the literature, considering the theoretical foundations distance learning and foreign and domestic experience. The rapid spread of remote education in the world not only opens up students and teachers great opportunities, but also creates a lot of problems. Students work autonomously, which raises many questions, such as: Does this lead to enough quality education? Are materials developed by specialist educators as effective and active for a distance student, as well as for a traditional students. The active participation of each student is a necessary aspect in learning. Students perform learning activities and at the same time reflect on the work to be done and its purpose, while improving their thinking abilities. All active learning methods are designed to solve the main problem - to develop critical thinking based on the analysis of professionally oriented situations, independent search for information, building a logical chain and making an informed decision. In teaching foreign languages, the principle activity acquires an important role, since mastering the target language is possible in that if each student is an active participant in the process, if he is involved in speech activity.

Active teaching methods are such teaching methods in which the student’s activity is productive, creative, search character. Active learning methods include didactic games, analysis of specific situations, problem solving, training in algorithm, brainstorming, out-of-context operations with concepts, etc.

¹ Tarnopolsky 2012: 20-71).

On active learning in general, there is an extensive scientific and pedagogical literature that is in demand in our time. The literature distinguishes between the concepts of active and interactive when learning foreign languages. Active learning versus passive learning different from interactive. Interactive training involves the presence of partners and the implementation of multi-vector contacts between all participants in the educational process (teachers, students, groups). Interactive methods can be seen as the most modern form of active methods.

Kolb's learning cycle. One of the most effective adult learning methods is

Kolb cycle. Psychologists David Kolb and Roger Fryem developed the model, teaching adults. Kolb Model – Theory adult education, aimed at the gradual formation of mental actions. She in widely used in various variations during interactive lessons¹. This model is suitable for anyone person, because the student already has: life experience that will help in learning, willingness to learn in order to achieve the desired goal, conscious learning. The Kolb method has been used in distance learning. So, the student who received this task, immediately chose the role of a thinker and discussed problematic issues. The student's response can be recorded in Audacity and sent for verification or it is produced with a Skype consultation. Professional opinion. Other new and specific way of active participation distance students in the discussion of issues in a foreign language is the reception "The opinion of a professional on the topic studied /problem." This didactic technique is suitable for adult students who already have a first (basic) specialty and professional experience as a lawyer, doctor, economist, architect and other students speak professionally on a single problem and give their solution based on the vision of their specialty. Yes, lawyer solves the problem from a legal point of view, an economist - from an economic point of view, a doctor - from a medical point of view, a translator - from a translation point of view. The answers are complete, balanced, reasoned, peculiar and unique. Answers are also recorded by students in Audacity or sent in writing.

Case study. A specific method of active teaching of foreign languages is case technology. The case study highlights four content components: problem, solution, situation and context². Case studies are valid method of activating the speech-cogitative activity of a distance student, since they imply the definition of a problem in a given situation and search for its solution. At such activities include mental operations of analysis, synthesis and evaluation. I know of a professional foreign language, case situations are systematically presented for independent analytical and educational-speech students' activities.

¹(Kolb 2011; McLeod 2013).

²Plotnikov 2014: 4

Example of case situations:

Case study. Choosing an educational trip in Uzbekistan.

Situation. You are a guide interpreter. You accompany a group of foreign visitors through the sights in Uzbekistan. While leading the tour, explain your tourists the main features and importance of the sights. Stress the role of Uzbekistan in contributing to the world heritage. State the problem and give a possible solution.

Student responses can be written, executed in different elements of the platform Moodle, or oral as an audio recording of foreign speech.

Reception of reflection. The technology of active learning also includes the technique of reflection. Reflective activity of remote student is a prerequisite teaching discipline in a foreign language.

The current reflection affects the student's reflections on the ongoing subject activity. at the final stage of the lesson, a situational task is offered for the student's reflection on the possibility of his future professional work as a translator in the field under study economics: Granty our time for reflection upon the role of

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